

An Analysis of Relationship with Non-Muslims in Islamic Sharia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 18, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 21, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Islam, Minorities, Relationship, Dealings, Islamic State</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5590124</p>	<p><i>Islam is a complete code of life because it has clear instructions for every walk of life. Since it allows the non-Muslims to live peacefully in an Islamic state, it has given them due rights as well as assigned responsibilities to them. This research work tries to explore what kind of relationships can be kept and dealings made with them by Muslims. Similarly, it also examines the extent of relationships and dealings with them, Muslims have been prohibited of. The Quran and the collection of Ahadith have been consulted in the first place in this regard. Tafaseer-e-Quran have also been searched out and quoted wherever needed for the said purpose. It has been found out that Islam has given them almost all the rights a Muslim enjoys in Islamic state and instructs the Muslims to be kind and affectionate toward them. It allows them to have good relationships with them however, it forbids them from having relationships with them which may harm Islam and its followers in any way.</i></p>

Introduction

Islam is the basis and law for leading life in an Islamic society. It has clear commands for every aspects of life and instructs about love, sympathy, tolerance, modesty, magnanimity and decorum in social life and strictly outlaws pride, prejudice, hate, narrow-mindedness and creating difficulties for others. It also aspires for pleasant relationship between Muslims and non-Muslims living in an Islamic state and endorses the rights of everyone including the minority. Islam not only has allowed the minorities to live in the Islamic state but also has taken the responsibility of their protection. They have been given the same rights what a Muslim citizen has. Islam does not discriminate between a Muslim and non-Muslim in its zero-tolerance policy toward cruelty against its citizen. The Holy Prophet (SAW) has said:

أَلَا مَنْ ظَلَمَ مُعَاهِدًا، أَوْ انْتَقَصَهُ، أَوْ كَلَّفَهُ فَوْقَ طَاقَتِهِ، أَوْ أَخَذَ مِنْهُ شَيْئًا بغيرِ طيبِ نَفْسٍ، فَأَنَا حَجِيبُهُ يَوْمَ الْقِيَامَةِ¹

Translation

“Beware, if anyone wrongs a contracted man, or diminishes his right, or forces him to work beyond his capacity, or takes from him anything without his consent, I shall plead for him on the Day of Judgement.”

As the minorities live in Islamic society, there arises the needs of dealings, agreements and other relations between them and Muslims. The Muslims are allowed to keep certain relations and make dealings with them but there are some dealings and relations which are not allowed. The questions are, what are the things in which one can help or take help of non-Muslims? What are the limits of the allowed and restricted things in this regard?

Following are some of the relations and dealings which are allowed by Sharea:

1. Their poor can be financially assisted.
2. Accepting and giving them gifts are allowed.
3. If they face any misfortune, one can condole them.
4. If they need residence, they can be provided home freely or on rent.
5. Taking their services or serving them is allowed.

Some of the dealings which are not allowed are mentioned below:

1. Helping them against the Muslims
2. Selling war equipment to them for fight against Muslims
3. To help them preach anti-Islamic ideas

This research work investigates to explore a detail account of the allowed and forbidden relations and dealings with them.

Relationships which are not allowed

It is very important to know that having no dislike for Kufr (infidelity) and keeping heartfelt friendship with non-Muslims are not allowed in Islamic Shari'a. According to Quran it is haram and a threat for Iman (faith). Quran says in this regards

{لَا تَجِدُ قَوْمًا يُؤْمِنُونَ بِاللَّهِ وَالْيَوْمِ الْآخِرِ يُوَادُّونَ مَنْ حَادَّ اللَّهَ وَرَسُولَهُ وَلَوْ كَانُوا آبَاءَهُمْ أَوْ أَبْنَاءَهُمْ أَوْ إِخْوَانَهُمْ أَوْ عَشِيرَتَهُمْ} ⁱⁱ

Translation:

“You will not find those who believe in Allah and in the hereafter having friendship with those who oppose Allah and his messenger, even though they may be their fathers or their sons or their brothers or their clan.”

The same is reinforced by the Holy Prophet (SAW) as he has said:

إِنَّ أَوْلَىٰ عُرَىٰ الْإِيمَانِ: الْمُوَالَاةُ فِي اللَّهِ , وَالْمُعَادَاةُ فِي اللَّهِ , وَالْحُبُّ فِي اللَّهِ , وَالْبُغْضُ فِي اللَّهِⁱⁱⁱ

Translation:

“Indeed the strong hook of chain of belief (Islam) is doing friendship and enmity and love and hate for the sake of Allah.”

and

مَنْ أَحَبَّ لِلَّهِ، وَأَبْغَضَ لِلَّهِ، وَأَعْطَىٰ لِلَّهِ، وَمَنَعَ لِلَّهِ فَقَدْ اسْتَكْمَلَ الْإِيمَانَ^{iv}

Translation:

“Whoever loves for the sake of Allah, hates for the sake of Allah, gives for the sake of Allah and withholds for the sake of Allah has perfected faith.”

According to the above mentioned verse and Ahadith having friendship and enmity for the sake of Allah is the part of faith and one cannot become a complete Muslim without considering the same.

According to the above mentioned principle of friendship and enmity for the sake of Allah there is some detail in having relationship with non-Muslims, ignoring which can risks for faith. It should be clear that in the life of the Holy Prophet (SAW) at Madina there were six different kinds of people. The Quran has clear instructions for having relationships with all these groups.

1. Real Momin

They were firm believers and consisted of Muhajireen and Ansaar. A very clear Quranic instruction about their mutual relationship is as under.

{إِنَّ الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا وَهَاجَرُوا وَجَاهَدُوا بِأَمْوَالِهِمْ وَأَنْفُسِهِمْ فِي سَبِيلِ اللَّهِ وَالَّذِينَ آوَوْا وَنَصَرُوا أُولَٰئِكَ بَعْضُهُمْ أَوْلِيَاءُ بَعْضٍ^v}

Translation:

“Surely those who believed and emigrated and carried out Jihad in the way of Allah with their wealth and lives, and those who gave refuge and help to (the emigrants), both are close friends to each other.”

2. Muslims who did not migrate to Madina

These were the people who had accepted Islam but had not migrated to the centre of Islam; Madina, and lived in their territories though they were directed to migrate to Madina and be united with the aforementioned group. Allah (SWT) says about them

{وَالَّذِينَ آمَنُوا وَلَمْ يُهَاجِرُوا مَا لَكُمْ مِنْ وَلَايَتِهِمْ مِنْ شَيْءٍ حَتَّىٰ يُهَاجِرُوا وَإِنِ اسْتَنْصَرُوكُمْ فِي الدِّينِ فَعَلَيْكُمُ النَّصْرُ إِلَّا عَلَىٰ قَوْمٍ بَيْنَكُمْ وَبَيْنَهُمْ مِيثَاقٌ^{vi}}

Translation:

“And those who believed and did not emigrate, you have no friendships with them at all, unless they emigrate. However, if they seek your help in the matter of faith, then you are bound to help, except against a people with whom you have a treaty.”

Relationship with such people was weak despite of being Muslims however, it was not completely cut off. The real believers were directed to help them in case they were oppressed by others, subject to certain conditions. If they had a fight with non-Muslims having pact of peace with Islamic state, the Islamic state was not allowed to fight in favour of such Muslims despite of having sympathy for them, against the said opponents. The reason is Islam gives extreme importance to peace agreements. If Islamic brotherhood hinders in practice over a peace treaty, the treaty would be given preference even if it is with non-Muslims.

والمعني انه لا يجوز لكم نصرهم عليهم اذالميثاق مانع من ذلك.^{vii}

Translation:

“It means that you are not allowed to help them (Muslim who have not migrated) against them (non-Muslims having treaty with) because the treaty prevents from doing so.”

The Hypocrite

The third group was that of hypocrite (Munafiqeen). They lived in Madina and its outskirts. They pretended to be Muslims however, they inwardly were non-Muslims. As they used to practice Islamic injunctions overtly, therefore, they were dealt as Muslims, for instance, once such a person objected over the distribution of the Holy Prophet (SAW), the companion of the Holy Prophet (SAW) in anger asked permission to kill him. The Holy Prophet (SAW) did not allow them asserting that he used to offer Salath. Hazrat Khalid bin Waleed (RA) said that there are a lot of people who offer Salath and speak well of Islam however, they don't hold Islam in their hearts. The Holy Prophet (SAW) replied

إِنِّي لَمْ أَوْمَرْ أَنْ أَنْقَبَ عَنْ قُلُوبِ النَّاسِ^{viii}

Translation:

“I have not been ordered (by Allah) to search the hearts of the people.”

4. Jews, Christians and Polytheists

The fourth, fifth and sixth groups were the followers of Judaism, Christianity and Polytheism. Quran forbids to have heartfelt friendship and love with them in the following verses.

{لَا يَتَّخِذِ الْمُؤْمِنُونَ الْكَافِرِينَ أَوْلِيَاءَ مِنْ دُونِ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ وَمَنْ يَفْعَلْ ذَلِكَ فَلَيْسَ مِنَ اللَّهِ فِي شَيْءٍ إِلَّا أَنْ يَتَّقُوا مِنْهُمْ تُقَاةً^{ix}}

Translation:

“The believers must not take the disbelievers as friends instead of the believers. And whoever does that has no relation with Allah whatsoever, unless you (do so) as a protective measure (in order to) save yourself from them.”

{ لَا تَجِدُ قَوْمًا يُؤْمِنُونَ بِاللَّهِ وَالْيَوْمِ الْآخِرِ يُوَادُّونَ مَنْ حَادَّ اللَّهَ وَرَسُولَهُ } x

Translation:

“You will not find those who believe in Allah and in the hereafter having friendship with those who oppose Allah and his messenger.”

{ يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا لَا تَتَّخِذُوا عَدُوِّي وَعَدُوَّكُمْ أَوْلِيَاءَ تُلْفُونَ إِلَيْهِمْ بِالْمَوَدَّةِ وَقَدْ كَفَرُوا بِمَا جَاءَكُمْ مِنَ الْحَقِّ } xi

Translation:

“O you who believe, do not take my enemies and your enemies for friends, expressing love with them, while they have rejected the truth that has come to you.”

It is clear from the above mentioned verses that keeping the following relationships with non-Muslims is illegitimate rather it is kufr.

1. Obeying nonbelievers in religious matters and paying no heed to the obligations of religion.
2. Making cooperation with them against Muslims.
3. Revering them because of their anti-Islamic beliefs and philosophies.
4. Accepting all their claims and assisting them in spreading their anti-Islamic beliefs.
5. Asking forgiveness for a deceased nonbeliever.
6. Keeping heartiest friendship with them in comparison to Muslims. A Muslim would have such relationship with Muslims, because it is the integral part of a Muslim's faith to love Allah, his messenger and all their beloved things and avoid all those things which are risky to this love. Furthermore, the love of two opposite things cannot be combined together.

Relationships which are allowed

The aforementioned verses and ahadith mean only that a Muslim should dislike the infidel beliefs and bad deeds of non-Muslims only. Furthermore, he should not obey them against Islamic Sharea, avoid their religious symbols and culture and not help them against Muslims, as Allah (SWT) says in Quran:

{ وَكَرِهَ إِلَيْكُمْ الْكُفْرَ وَالْفُسُوقَ وَالْعِصْيَانَ } xii

Translation:

“And made detestable to you the disbelief and sins and disobedience.”

The said verses and ahadith never mean that doing injustice to them is allowed, as Allah (SWT) has forbidden Muslims from it the following verses:

{ يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا كُونُوا قَوَّامِينَ لِلَّهِ شُهَدَاءَ بِالْقِسْطِ وَلَا يَجْرِمَنَّكُمْ شَنَاَنُ قَوْمٍ عَلَىٰ أَلَّا تَعْدِلُوا اعْدِلُوا هُوَ أَقْرَبُ لِلتَّقْوَىٰ } xiii

Translation:

“O you who believe, be steadfast for (obeying the commands of) Allah, (and) witnesses for justice. Malice against a people should not prompt you to avoid doing justice. Do justice. That is nearer to *Taqwa*.”

{ لَا يَنْهَاكُمْ اللَّهُ عَنِ الَّذِينَ لَمْ يُقَاتِلُوكُمْ فِي الدِّينِ وَلَمْ يُخْرِجُوكُمْ مِنْ دِيَارِكُمْ أَنْ تَبَرُّوهُمْ وَتُقْسِطُوا إِلَيْهِمْ إِنَّ اللَّهَ يُحِبُّ الْمُقْسِطِينَ } xiv

Translation:

“Allah does not forbid you as regards those who did not fight you on account of faith, and did not expel you from your homes, that you do well to them, and deal justly with them. Surely Allah loves those who maintain justice.”

{ وَلَا تُجَادِلُوا أَهْلَ الْكِتَابِ إِلَّا بِالَّتِي هِيَ أَحْسَنُ } xv

Translation:

“And do not debate with the people of the book unless it is in the best manner.”

Here is detailed analysis of permitted relationships and dealing with non-Muslims in the light of Islamic Jurisprudence.

Education

Islam allows Muslim students to get education from non-Muslims if necessary, provided that they protect their beliefs and act according to the principles of Islam. Similarly, non-Muslims can be accommodated in educational institutes of Muslims provided that all their activities revolve around education and their aim is not sabotaging and harming the country.

Travel to non-Muslim countries

Travel to and residence in non-Muslim countries which are bound in pacts are allowed provided that there is no danger to one's Deen and freedom to practice it is not denied. Non-Muslim countries which are not under any such contract can also be visited for the purpose of preaching, diplomacy and trade etc. The Holy Prophet (SAW) used to send letters and messages through his diplomats to non-Muslims.^{xvi}

Hazrat Abu Bakr (RA) also went to the non-Muslims of Syria for trade purposes along with his companions Hazrat Nuaiman (RA) and Hazrat Swaibit (RA), a year before the demise of the Holy Prophet (SAW) however, there is no such evidence that He had prevented him.^{xvii}

Majority of the Jurisprudents have the same opinion that travel for commercial and other just compulsory reasons to non-Muslim countries and residing there as per need is allowed.^{xviii}

Doing job with non-Muslims

Fiqh Islami (Islamic Jurisprudence) allows a Muslim in financial constraints to work with non-Muslims with trustworthiness and honesty provided that he acts upon his religion. Serving non-Muslims and keeping relations with them is allowed as per the responsibility assigned to him. According to Sahih Bukhari and Sahih Muslim Hazrat Khabbab bin Art (RA) used to live in Makkah and worked as a blacksmith for the non-Muslims.^{xix}

Quran describes about Hazrat Yousaf (AS) that he requested the Pharaoh of Egypt to grant him the finance ministry and worked as finance minister for years.

Allama Qurtabi in the explanation of the verse says:

قَالَ بَعْضُ أَهْلِ الْعِلْمِ: فِي هَذِهِ الْآيَةِ مَا يُبَيِّحُ لِلرَّجُلِ الْفَاضِلِ أَنْ يَعْمَلَ لِلرَّجُلِ الْفَاجِرِ، وَالسُّلْطَانِ الْكَافِرِ، بِشَرْطِ أَنْ يَعْلَمَ أَنَّهُ يُفَوِّضُ إِلَيْهِ فِي فِعْلٍ لَا يُعَارِضُهُ فِيهِ، فَيُصْلِحُ مِنْهُ مَا شَاءَ^{xx}

Translation:

“Some of the scholars in the interpretation of this verse say that it is legal for a pious person to work with an impious person or with a non-Muslim ruler provided that he is sure that he would not be assigned any task in contradiction to his faith and he would strive for correction.”

Similarly if some Muslims were living in a non-Muslim state and they need a Muslim judge, so the Jurisprudents have allowed him to take oath of Justices as per the law of that non-Muslim country and accordingly perform responsibilities.

ويجوز تقلد القضاء من السلطان العادل والجا نر ولوا كافرًا-xxi

Translation:

“Accepting judicial post from fair, unjust and non-believer ruler is allowed.”

Same is the case with other fields like education and health etc.

3. Employing a non-Muslim

Most of the jurisprudents allow to hire a non-Muslim if needed. The Holy Prophet (SAW) at the time of migrating to Madina hired the services of a non-Muslim to lead him toward Madina.^{xxii}

Allama Ibne Hajar (RA) says:

عامّة الفقهاء يُجيزُونَ اسْتِئْجَارَهُمْ [المشركين] عِنْدَ الصَّرُورَةِ وَغَيْرِهَا^{xxiii}

Translation:

“Most of the jurisprudents allow taking services from non-believers in need and otherwise.”

He further says:

وَفِي الْحَدِيثِ جَوَازُ اسْتِئْجَادِ الْمُشْرِكِ^{xxiv}

Translation:

“There is permission in hadith regarding taking services from non-believers.”

The jurisprudents say that even Quran can be transcribed by non-Muslims. In this regard two sayings from Imam Ahmad(RA) and one from Ahnaf are narrated.^{xxv}

4. Baby-care and breastfeeding by non-Muslim woman

Majority of the jurisprudents allow to assign the responsibilities of caring and breastfeeding to a Muslim child to a non-Muslim woman. Allama Kasani says in this regards:

وَلَا بَأْسَ بِاسْتِئْجَارِ ظَنَرٍ كَافِرَةٍ، وَالَّتِي وَلَدَتْ مِنْ فُجُورٍ؛ لِأَنَّ الْكُفْرَ وَالْفُجُورَ لَا يُؤْتَرَانِ فِي اللَّبَنِ^{xxvi}

Translation:

“There is no harm in taking the services of non-believer wet nurse and that who is born out of wedlock, as Kufri and Fujur do not have any influence in milk.”

The jurisprudents of Malikia school of thought and Hassan Basri (RA) have the same opinion.^{xxvii}

Likewise if segregation occurs between a Muslim and his non-Muslim wife (Christian or Jew) due to some reasons, she has the right just like a Muslim mother to keep her immature children (boy upto the age of seven and girl upto the age of nine years) under her custody. The husband in this duration cannot take his children under his custody without her consent or will.^{xxviii}

Seeking asylum with non-Muslims

If a Muslim’s life or wealth are endangered and he has no other option than to take asylum with a non-Muslim, so he is allowed rather it is obligatory for him to do that, provided that he is not compelled to act against Islam. The Holy Prophet (SAW) has taken asylum with his uncle Abu Talib and another non-Muslim Mataam bin Adi.^{xxix} Similarly Hazrat Abu Bakr (RA) took asylum with a non-Muslim named Ibn al Daghina.

Giving political asylum to non-Muslims

Islamic state can offer political asylum to a Muslim rather in some cases it becomes obligatory if he/ she feels threatened for his/her life and/ or religion or he/she is degraded in a non-Muslim country. The ruler of Islamic state has the authority to confer it on non-Muslims seeking political asylum in Muslim state.

Likewise if a Muslim gets asylum in a non-Muslim state due to some valid reasons like threat to his/her life or economic hardships, the Islamic state would not take any negative step against him/her. However, if he joins non-Muslims in harming Muslims then he does not remain Muslim and having friendship/ relationship with him/her is not allowed rather it leads to Kufr.^{xxx}

Exchange of war prisoners

Islam has given the authority to the Muslim ruler to either let the war prisoner free as a gesture of goodwill or as an exchange for Muslims war prisoners in the custody of non-Muslims. Majority of the jurists declare the exchange of war prisoners as lawful while Imam Abu Hanifa (RA) disallows it.^{xxxii}

Examples can be found from the Seerat of the Holy Prophet (SAW) as well as his companions arrested a non-Muslim from Banu Aqeel, the Holy Prophet (SAW) set him free in exchange for the release of two Muslims.^{xxxiii}

Pacts with non-Muslims

There are several kinds of pacts with non-Muslims according to Islamic jurisprudence. The detail is as follows.

1. Pact with Dhimmi (non-Muslims living in Islamic state with legal protection)

Dhimmi, collectively ahl ad-dhimmah or Mu'ahid literally means "protected person" is a term for non-Muslims living in an Islamic state with legal protection, who is bound to respect and act upon the laws of the country. According to the agreement they have to pay certain amount as tax called Jizia and are entitled to the rights all other citizens are entitled to. By law they have to be treated with respect and any discrimination against them and dilapidation is not allowed. Apart from their religious activities help and participation in their routine activities is allowed.

2. Criminal-exchange Pact

Exchange of criminals with countries which are not in any such treaty is not allowed both in Islam as well as international laws. The jurists, however, have different opinions regarding the exchange of prisoners with those non-Muslim state which are in any such pact with the Muslim state. It is not allowed according to Hanafi and some of the Maliki schools of thoughts' jurists to hand over a Muslim or a Dhimmi criminal to a non-Muslim state.^{xxxiii}

On the other hand Hanabila and the majority of Maliki schools of thoughts' jurists any such treaty is allowed and obligatory to be acted upon on equal footing if the second party also fulfils the obligations of the treaty.^{xxxiv}

An example can be traced in this regard from the practice of the Holy Prophet (SAW) when on the occasion of the treaty of Hudaibia he handed over two Muslims; Abu Jundul (RA) and Abu Baseer (RA) to Quraish as per exchange of criminal treaty.^{xxxv}

3. Pact for Exchange of Secret Information

It is not allowed for an Islamic state to provide secret information to non-Muslims which are harmful to the state and/ or its citizens. It is not restricted to Islam only as all the religions disallow it. However, the exchange of information which are not harmful to the state and its citizens and can be beneficial for non-Muslims are allowed to be exchanged with them for example the number of citizens, general news and the number of students in educational institutions etc. As one of the clauses of "The Madina Pact" is (ان بينهم النصح) (that the Jews and the Muslims will have a relationship of benevolence, so the above mentioned are also included in the same.^{xxxvi}

4. Peace-Pacts during Wars

Islam does not want to start a war with non-Muslim, prolong it and may not be ended rather Quran says:

{ وَإِنْ جَنَحُوا لِلسَّلْمِ فَاجْنَحْ لَهَا وَتَوَكَّلْ عَلَى اللَّهِ }^{xxxvii}

Translation:

"And if they tilt towards peace, you too should tilt towards them and place your trust in Allah."

All the jurists are of the opinion that peace treaty is allowed in need. Apart from need some of the jurists allow it if there is an additional benefit or expediency, while some other are of the opinion that whenever the non-Muslims offer peace treaty and there is no harm to Muslims from it, the Muslim ruler is authorized to accept it.^{xxxviii}

Furthermore, according to the majority of the jurists if the treaty is for a certain period, the Muslims should abide by the rules of the treaty provided that the other party does not effract and violate openly. The Muslim ruler cannot terminate the treaty one-sidedly as Allah (SWT) orders Muslims in Quran:

{ يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا أَوْفُوا بِالْعُقُودِ }^{xxxix}

Translation:

"O you who believe, fulfil the contracts."

According to Ahnaf the Muslim ruler has the authority to terminate it however, with the condition to clearly inform the other party about the termination of the said treaty. The termination of the treaty while keeping the opponent party in dark is Haraam (forbidden in Islamic law). All the jurists are of the opinion that both the side will have the rights of peace within the duration of treaty and their lives and wealth will have the same protection what it had before the war.^{x1}

5. Peace-Pact with the Conquered People without War

War is not the prime concern of Islam rather spreading the message of ultimate reality. If the people of certain area don't want to fight and offer peace treaty, the Muslims should accept it. In case of treaty, there are two options according to Islamic sharea. One is to declare continued their ownership on their property and give them proprietary rights however, they would have to pay a very meagre amount as an annual tax (Jizia).

Second one is that the land would be considered the property of Muslims. It would however, remain with them and they would be allowed to live in and use it with a condition to pay annual tax (Khiraj) as per the size and scope of the land. Meanwhile, if someone among them accepts Islam, he/she would be exempted from the financial burden and would be treated like any other Muslim. The Holy Prophet (SAW) did the same with the Jews of Khyber when he accepted their request to leave them on their lands in consideration of annual Khiraj.^{xli}

In the first case only Ahnaf consider the land as the part of Islamic state and believe in protecting their social and citizenship rights, imposing a very small amount as Jizia annually. However, no other tax or Khiraj would be taken from the income of their lands.

In the second case according to all the jurists the land would be considered as the part of Islamic state however, no other tax would be taken from them except for Khiraj (tax from the income of the land). They would have all the rights a Muslim citizen has. In either cases, the land would not be taken from them unless they remain loyal to the pact.^{xlii}

6. Trade with non-Muslims

Trade-relations among nations and countries have always been considered important for their survival and development. The economic strength of the global village has become so interconnected that it has become difficult for a country to survive without becoming part of it. Islamic fiqh is much comprehensive with reference to trade and commerce just like other fields of life and has ample solutions for all sorts of complications in this regards. It allows trade-relations with non-Muslims. The author of Kashf al Asrar says:

ولهذا... كان الكافر أهلاً لأحكام لا يبراد بها وجه الله مثل المعاملات والعقوبات^{xliii}

Translation:

“Therefore, ... A non-believer is allowed to be treated in the matters which are not meant for the sake of Allah, like dealings and punishments.”

Similarly, travel to non-Muslim states for the purpose of trade is allowed.^{xliiv}

Likewise, agreements of trade are also allowed as it is for buying and selling which is allowed from the examples of the life of the Holy Prophet (SAW). Hazrat Aisha (RA) says in this regards:

عن عائشة رضي الله عنها: أن النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم «اشتري من يهودي طعاما إلى أجل، ورهنه درعه»^{xlv}

Translation:

“Narrated Aisha (RA) that The Prophet (SAW) bought some foodstuff on credit for a limited period and mortgaged his armour for it.”

Similarly Hazrat Abdul Rahman bin Abi Bakr (RA) narrates:

عن عبد الرحمن بن أبي بكر رضي الله عنهما... ثم جاء رجل مشرك طويل بغنم يسوقها... فاشتري منه شاة^{xlvi}

Translation:

“Narrated `Abdur-Rahman bin Abu Bakr (RA): ...when a tall pagan with long matted unkempt hair came driving his sheep... The Prophet (SAW) bought a sheep from him.”

Tax relief for non-Muslims for the promotion of trade

Following are some of the guidelines of Islamic Sharea for concession with non-Muslims regarding trade tax;

1. They would exempted from tax if declared indebted.
2. Tax would not collected of the goods costing less than 200 Dirhams.
3. Muslim ruler is authorized to reduce the amount of the tax or exempt it totally.
4. The maximum limit of the tax from non-Muslims should not exceed from the amount of the tax taken from Muslim businessmen according to Imam Abu Hanifa (RA).^{xlvii}

Conclusion:

Islam is a complete code of life and it has clear instructions for every walk of life. Since it allows the non-Muslims to live peacefully in Islamic state, it has very clearly demarcated rights and obligations for them. Similarly it has very clear instructions for Muslims what kind of relations they must/can keep with them and what not. In spite of dislike for the kufr of non-Muslims, Islam not only allows but also inspires them for some of the following relationships.

1. The Muslims should be kind toward them and treat them politeness and respect particularly those who are in peace treaty with them.
2. Financial assistance should be given to their poor and destitute ones.
3. They should be given gifts and their gifts should be accepted.
4. Condole their grieved ones and assuage them. Similarly express happiness on their legitimate happiness.
5. Greet them and answer their fair greetings.
6. Financial dealings and pacts can be done with them.

7. House for residence can be given to them with or without payment provided that it is used for residential purposes and not for sedition and deviation.
8. They can be offered paid jobs. Similarly free services can be accepted from them.
9. Going to and stay in their countries for a just reason is allowed provided that there is no risk to faith.
10. In case they stop war and give Jizia, they should be allowed to live in Muslim countries with religious freedom.
11. Peace treaty should be signed with them if they offer.
12. Protection should be provided to their lives and wealth in case of peace treaty. If a Muslim commits a crime in this regards, he should be punished and the non-Muslim should be compensated.
13. There is no harm in having interactions with them provided that religious values are not compromised.
14. Learning knowledge with them and mutual cooperation in this regard is allowed.
15. Use of slaughtered animals in the name of Allah by Jews and Christian is allowed. Similarly wedding Jewish and Christian women is also legal.
16. Dealing with their trustworthy persons is allowed. Similarly they can be trusted in worldly matters.
17. Muslims should take care of the rights of their non-Muslim relatives.
18. Employment with them and offering them employment are allowed.
19. They are entitled to all judicial rights which a Muslim enjoys.
20. They are entitled to all educational, commercial and economic rights which a Muslim enjoys.

Following is a list of some of the relationships and dealings which are not allowed to be kept with non-Muslims.

1. Obeying nonbelievers in religious matters and paying no heed to the obligations of religion.
2. Cooperating them against Muslims.
3. Revering them because of their anti-Islamic beliefs and philosophies.
4. Accepting all their claims and assisting them in spreading their anti-Islamic beliefs.
5. Asking forgiveness for a deceased nonbeliever.
6. Keeping heartiest friendship with them in comparison to Muslims. A Muslim would have such relationship with Muslims, because it is the integral part of a Muslim's faith to love Allah, his messenger and all their beloved things and avoid all those things which are risky to this love. Furthermore, the love of two opposite things cannot be combined together.

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